

which the probability of a good response to added fertilizer is high, and above which the probability is low.

The critical level of a particular nutrient is determined as follows:

$$\text{Yield (\%)} = \frac{\text{Yield without nutrient}}{\text{Yield with applied nutrient}} \times 100.$$

The method consists of superimposing

two intersecting lines on the soil test percent yield scatter diagram – one line parallel to the y -axis and the other to the x -axis, drawn in a manner that places the maximum number of points in the lower left and upper right quadrants. The point where the line drawn parallel to the y -axis cuts the x -axis is termed the critical level.

This approach was used with data from the field trials to establish critical

levels for organic carbon, available phosphorus, and exchangeable potassium in Sierra Leone's two dominant rice ecologies: uplands (41 trials) and inland valley swamps (19 trials).

Tables 1 and 2 indicate that fields with less than 2.4% organic carbon, 10 ppm phosphorus, and 0.07 meq exchangeable potassium/100 g soil should respond positively to the corresponding plant nutrients. ■

Nitrogen management in coarse-textured lowland rice soils

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Field studies on nitrogen efficiency have been in progress at this center under the International Network for Soil Fertility

and Fertilizer Evaluation in Rice (INSFFER) Program for the last two seasons. Under the program various nitrogen sources and application methods to rice have been tested on a red sandy loam soil (Alfisol) of intermediate fertility.

Among the several treatments listed, subsoil application of urea gave the best performance at both low and high nitrogen levels (see table). Mudball or supergranule application resulted in

equivalent grain yields. The response to sulfur-coated urea (SCU) was equally encouraging.

Nitrogen efficiency was highest with mudball application. Supergranule and SCU application gave comparable N efficiency. ■

Effects of sources of nitrogen and methods of application on rice yields and nitrogen efficiency, Mandya, Karnataka, 1977 and 1978 kharif.

Source	Method	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)			
		1977 kharif		1978 kharif	
		Low N, 28 kg N/ha	High N, 56 kg N/ha	Low N, 27 kg N/ha	High N, 54 kg N/ha
Control	No nitrogen	2.42 (00)	—	3.50 (00)	—
Urea	Best split (50%, 25%, and 25% N, at planting, tillering, and PI stage)	2.78 (13)	3.21 (14)	4.72 (45)	4.60 (20)
Urea	Basal – band placement in every other row	2.88 (17)	2.84 (8)	—	—
Urea	Basal – mudball for every pair of rows, 10–12 cm soil depth	4.16 (62)	4.83 (43)	—	—
Urea	Basal – supergranules for every pair of rows, 10–12 cm soil depth	3.79 (49)	4.65 (40)	5.12 (60)	5.87 (44)
Urea	Basal – plow sole application	—	—	5.15 (61)	5.72 (41)
SCU	Basal – broadcasting and incorporation	3.74 (47)	4.25 (33)	4.36 (32)	5.44 (36)
SCU	Basal – plow sole application	—	—	4.87 (51)	5.94 (45)
SCU	Basal – broadcasting and incorporation	—	—	4.45 (35)	5.39 (35)

^aFigures in parentheses indicate the nitrogen efficiency in kilogram grain/kilogram of applied N. Kharif = wet season. PI = panicle initiation.

	IR20	Rasi
General mean yield (t/ha)	3.55	5.03
CD at 0.05	0.63	0.64
CV (%)	12.70	10.00

Effect of azolla inoculation on rice yields

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The water fern azolla, in association with the blue-green algae *Anabaena azollae*, can fix atmospheric nitrogen and supply it to the rice crop after decomposition. The effects of azolla incorporation on rice yield were studied. A field experiment using IR20 was conducted in a randomized block design with four replications in the 1978–79navarai season. Treatments were:

- 0-50-50 kg NPK/ha
- 25-50-50 kg NPK/ha
- 50-50-50 kg NPK/ha
- 75-50-50 kg NPK/ha
- 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha
- 0-50-50 kg NPK/ha + azolla
- 25-50-50 kg NPK/ha + azolla
- 50-50-50 kg NPK/ha + azolla
- 75-50-50 kg NPK/ha + azolla
- 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha + azolla

Urea, superphosphate and muriate of potash were used as sources of N, P, and K. Seven days after transplanting, 300 g azolla/m² was inoculated. In about 2 weeks azolla covered the plot surface and was incorporated.

Azolla incorporation increased yields